

LOCALISED EFFECTS IN COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURES: MODELLING AND EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERISATION OF LOAD RESPONSE, FAILURE AND FATIGUE

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SUMMARY

The objective is to provide an overview of the mechanisms that determine the occurrence and severity of localized effects in sandwich structures. The experimental characterisation and modelling of local effects in sandwich structures is addressed based on the generic case of sandwich structures with internal core junctions under general loading conditions. The issue of failure and fatigue phenomena induced by the presence of core junctions will be discussed in detail with the inclusion of recent theoretical and experimental results.

Keywords: Sandwich structures; Local effects; Core junctions; Stress concentrations; Failure criteria; Fatigue

INTRODUCTION

Structural sandwich panels can be considered as a special type of composite laminate where two thin, stiff, strong and relatively dense face sheets, which are often by themselves composite laminates, are separated by and bonded to a thick, lightweight and compliant core material. Sandwich structures have gained widespread acceptance as an excellent way to obtain lightweight components and structures with very high bending stiffness, high strength and high buckling resistance [1].

At the same time sandwich structures are notoriously sensitive to failure by the application of concentrated loads, at points or lines of support, and due to localized effects induced in the vicinity of points of geometric and material discontinuities [1-6]. The reason for this is that, although sandwich structures are well suited for the transfer of overall bending and shearing loads, local effects as mentioned above induce severe through-thickness shear and normal stresses. These through-thickness stress components can be of significant magnitude, and may in some cases approach or exceed the allowable stresses in the core material as well as in the interfaces between the core and the face sheets [2-6]. In addition, localized bending effects may induce in-plane stress concentrations in the face sheets, which, depending on the loading situation and the boundary conditions, may exceed the “globally” induced stresses, and thereby endanger the structural integrity.

Local effects may be induced in sandwich structures due to geometric and material discontinuities associated with various types of internal sub-structures including inserts and

backing plates (load introductions), edge inserts, core junctions and transissions from sandwich to monolithic laminate configurations as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Sandwich panel with geometrical and material discontinuities in the form of typical internal sub-structures.

The case of sandwich structures with internal core junctions (see Fig. 1) represents a generic case of localised effects. Here the local effects are induced by the mismatch of elastic properties of adjoining materials in sandwich core junctions (Fig. 1), and they cause an increase of the face sheet in-plane stresses as well as of the shear and through-the-thickness stresses in the adjacent cores [2]. Depending on the type of loading and the configuration of the sandwich structure, the stress concentrations may cause local fracture of the core materials, but local face failure or interface failure are also possible scenarios. The influence of such local effects on the structural integrity has been studied under both quasi-static and fatigue loading conditions for sandwich structures subjected to transverse shear loading in [3-4].

In the following, a brief survey of recent results concerning the experimental characterisation and modelling of local effects in sandwich structures with internal core junctions (see Fig. 1) under in-plane and transverse shear loading conditions will be given. The issue of failure and fatigue phenomena caused by the presence of core junctions will be discussed in some detail. The results presented are largely based on the work presented in [2-6] in general and on the work presented by Jakobsen et al. [7] and Johannes et al. [8, 9] and in particular.

IN-PLANE LOADING – QUASI-STATIC/FATIGUE TEST AND FEA RESULTS

This section focuses on local effects induced at a junction between two different core materials in sandwich panels subjected to tensile in-plane loading, a secondary load case which often occurs in practice. A preliminary investigation of this was presented by Bozhevolnaya et al. [5-6]. The influence of local effects on the failure behaviour under quasi-static as well as fatigue loading conditions will be discussed for typical sandwich configurations. For details see [7,8].

Five different sandwich beam configurations have been used to examine the influence of the local effects caused by core junctions under tensile loading conditions. The specimen configurations are specified in Fig. 2 and Table 1, where h_f and h_c denote the face and core thicknesses, respectively, and n_{static} and $n_{fatigue}$ are the number of specimens used for the quasi-static and fatigue testing, respectively.

Typical failure modes observed in the tensile tests are shown in Fig. 3. Various modeling techniques can be used for the analysis of localized effects, but for this study nonlinear finite element analyses (FEA) were conducted. The nonlinear modelling adopted geometrical nonlinearity (large deformations and rotations) as well as nonlinear material behaviour (e.g. material plasticity). Both 2D and a 3D FEA studies were conducted. However, the results quoted

herein are limited to 2D plane stress modelling for simplicity [7]. Isoparametric 2D 8-node PLANE 183 elements in ANSYS were used for the finite element mesh of the 2D model. The FE mesh (Fig. 4) was refined at the core junction to obtain sufficiently small element edge lengths that ensure convergence of the results.

Figure 2. Schematic of the dog bone shaped specimens used in the tensile tests; top: specimen for configuration 1a/b; bottom: specimen for configuration 2a/b [8]

Table 1. Considered sandwich beam configurations [8]

Config.	Face Material	Core Material 1	Core Material 2	h_f [mm]	h_c [mm]	w [mm]	n_{static}	$n_{fatigue}$
1a	Aluminium 7075-T6	Divinycell H60	Divinycell H200	0.4	25	10	3	5
1b	Aluminium 7075-T6	Rohacell 51WF	Rohacell 200WF	0.4	25	10	3	-
2a	GFRP, NCF [0/90] _s	Divinycell H60	Divinycell H200	1.0	25	20	3	8
2b	GFRP, NCF [0/90] _s	Divinycell H200	Plywood	1.0	25	20	6	5

Table 2 presents the results of the tensile tests (average values) and the results of the nonlinear FEA studies. A large number of studies concerning the failure behaviour of sandwich structures as well as the material and failure behaviour of sandwich constituent materials have been published in recent years [10-22]. This includes stress and strain based failure criteria or critical strain energy release rate considerations, but very few attempts have been made to address the prediction of failure associated with localised effects. This paper presents the failure predictions obtained using two failure criteria; maximum principal stress and maximum principal strain, respectively, for both the faces and the core materials, see [7, 8] for details. The different results from the stress and strain criteria can be explained by the internal procedure of the FEA program to calculate the stiffness matrix. With increasing load, the stiffness matrix is updated using the stress-strain data that was input as the material model, i.e. the stiffness matrix is dependent on the stress/strain level.

From Fig. 3 and Table 2 it is seen that failure occurred directly at or in the vicinity of the junction for most of the tested sandwich configurations, thus showing that the local effects at the core junction/discontinuity did have a significant influence on the failure behaviour under in-

plane tensile loading. Moreover, the nonlinear FE analyses capture the nonlinear material and failure behaviour very well in an overall sense, and also the predicted failure loads are reasonably accurate [8]. In Table 2 the numbers marked with **bold** indicate the location of failure and the predicted max. principal stress or strain values at failure.

Figure 3. Images of typical failure observed in quasi-static tensile tests [8].

Table 2. Failure loads and stresses/strains predicted by nonlinear FEA and point stress/strain criteria [8].

Con-fig..	Exp. failure load [N]	Exp. (first) Failure location	Maximum principal stress criterion				Maximum principal strain criterion			
			Predicted failure load [N]	Maximum principal stresses [MPa]			Predicted failure load [N]	Maximum principal strains [%]		
				Face sheet	Compl. core	Stiff core		Face sheet	Compl. core	Stiff core
1a	4444	Compl. core / Junction	4450	540	1.3	4.3	4550	5.0	5.9	1.0
1b	4085	Compl. core / Junction	4250	475	1.4	3.4	-	-	-	-
2a	17831	Face sheet / Arbitr. location	4250	475	1.4	3.4	17900	2.4	4.5	2.0
2b	11801	Compl. core / Junction	11800	310	6.3	69	11800	1.5	2.6	0.8

In addition to the quasi-static test a series of fatigue test were conducted as well. The tests were run with a sinusoidal load, a frequency of 3 Hz and a loading ratio $R=0.1$. Table 3 gives an overview over the chosen fatigue loads and the resulting failure behaviour and fatigue life times. In the quasi-static tests, the failure modes were dependent of the particular material configuration studied, whereas in the fatigue tests visible failure was always confined to the face sheets. Depending on the sandwich configuration, premature failure at the core junction was observed in

the experiments for quasi-static (Table 2) as well as fatigue loading conditions (Table 3). For a part of the tested configurations, the failure mode shifted from core failure in the quasi-static tests to face failure in the fatigue tests. In the fatigue tests, failure at the core junction was accompanied by a reduced fatigue life.

Figure 4. Sketch of a sandwich core junction and the 2D FE mesh at the tri-material corner [8]

Table 3. Fatigue test results – tensile loading

Config.	Fatigue load F_{dyn} [N]	$F_{dyn} / F_{stat,max}$	Fatigue life \pm Std. dev	Failure mode	Failure location
1a	2700	0.6	27877 ± 3691	Face failure	Arbitrary (5 of 5/5)
2a	7100	0.4	17282 ± 1026	Face failure	Junction (3 of 6/8)
	7100	0.4	19687	Face failure	Arbitrary (1 of 6/8)
	8900	0.5	7900	Face failure	Junction (1 of 6/8)
	11590	0.65	593	Face failure	Junction (1 of 6/8)
2b	7100	0.6	4654	Face failure	Junction (1 of 3/5)

Reference is given to [8] for full details concerning the quasi-static and fatigue test results, the FEA based failure analyses and the assessment of failure criteria for sandwich panels with internal core junctions subjected to in-plane loading.

TRANSVERSE SHEAR LOADING - QUASI-STATIC AND FATIGUE TEST RESULTS

This section focuses on local effects induced at junction between two different core materials in sandwich panels subjected to transverse shear loading, which is a very important load case. A preliminary investigation of this was presented by Bozhevlnaya et al. [2-6]. The influence of local effects on the failure behaviour under quasi-static as well as fatigue loading conditions is be discussed for typical sandwich configurations. For full details see [9].

Six sandwich beam configurations were considered in the experimental investigation. All configurations contained GFRP face sheets using a bidirectional stitched non crimp fabric (NCF). The lay-up was symmetric and balanced using either two or four layers of the NCF with a stacking sequence $[0/90]_s$ or $[0/90]_{2s}$, respectively. The resulting face sheet thickness was 1 mm or 2 mm, respectively. The core layer was either 10 mm or 25 mm thick, and contained two different core materials in three sections as shown in Fig. 5, forming two core junctions between the different cores. Table 4 specifies the specimen configurations.

The six specimen configurations can be separated in two groups with respect to their failure behaviour. The first group (Configs. 1-4) represents the most common sandwich configurations using low density semi-brittle PVC foam core. The deformation behaviour was dominated by shear deformations, and for all specimens of this group failure occurred by core shear in both the quasi-static tests, see Table 5 and Fig. 6. Here, the inherent core shear stresses under transverse loading outcompetes the local effects with respect to being most critical in terms of causing failure (cracking). High-speed video recordings document the core shear failure and proof that failure was not associated with the local effects for this group of specimens.

Figure 5. Schematic of sandwich beam specimens with core junctions; top: butt junction; bottom: 2x45° double scarf junction [9]

Table 4. Considered sandwich configurations [9]

Config.	Core material 1	Core material 2	Core junction shape	h_f [mm]	h_c [mm]	l_{core2} [mm]	Core stiffness ratio G_{core1} / G_{core2}
1	Divinycell H60	Divinycell H200	Butt junction	2.0	25	140	22 / 90
2	Divinycell H60	Aluminium	Butt junction	2.0	25	140	22 / 27000
3	Divinycell H60	Aluminium	2x45° junction	2.0	25	150	22 / 27000
4	Divinycell H60		No junction	2.0	25	-	(1/1)
5	Divinycell H200	Aluminium	Butt junction	1.0	10	100	90 / 27000

The second group of specimens belonged to Config. 5 which comprised a relatively thin and strong core material and thin face sheets, see Table 4. The deformation behaviour was dominated by bending deformations, see Fig. 6, and for the specimens of this group the dominant failure mode was face failure, see Table 5. The experimental results showed that the local effects significantly influenced the failure behaviour for this group of specimens, see Table 5 and Fig. 6. Thus, the stress concentrations in the face sheets at the core junctions lead to reduced failure loads under quasi-static loading.

The experimental observations have been substantiated by detailed finite element based failure analyses [9] in which various failure criteria were evaluated including the max. shear stress, principal stress, Christensen and Tsai-Wu criteria [10,11,16,17,18,21]. However, it is shown in

[9] that multiaxial failure criteria proposed for foam core materials have significant deficiencies when used for predicting the failure of sandwich structures with stress concentrations.

In addition to the quasi-static test a series of fatigue test were conducted [9]. The objective of the fatigue tests was to examine whether it is possible to observe and record fatigue failure behaviour that is associated with local effects at core junctions. The fatigue tests were run in load-control using the same setup as used in the quasi-static tests. The loading was sinusoidal with a loading ratio $R=0.1$ and a frequency of 3 Hz for configurations 1-4, and of 1.5 Hz for configurations 5. The maximum applied load was 50-76% of the mean failure loads observed in the quasi-static tests [9]. For Configs. 1-4 fatigue failure was in all cases caused by core shear. For Config. 5 all specimens failed by fatigue failure of the top face at the location of the core junction, i.e. due to fatigue stresses induced by the localised effects. Thus, the stress concentrations in the face sheets at the core junctions lead to reduced failure loads under both quasi-static loading and to fatigue damage accumulation and reduced fatigue lives under fatigue loading conditions.

Figure 6. Typical failure behaviour in the quasi-static tests, configurations 1-5 [9]

Reference is given to [9] for full details concerning the quasi-static and fatigue test results, the FEA based failure analyses and the assessment of failure criteria for sandwich panels with internal core junctions subjected to transverse shear loading.

Table 5. Average failure loads, failure modes and failure location in the quasi-static tests [9]

Config.	Core material 1	Core material 2	Junction shape	Specimen batch	Failure load [N] ± Std. dev.	Failure mode / location
1	Divinycell H60	Divinycell H200	Butt junction	1	942 ± 11	Core shear failure of core 1
				2	1222 ± 69	Core shear failure of core 1
				3	1446 ± 44	Core shear failure of core 1
2	Divinycell H60	Aluminium	Butt junction	4	1136 ± 69	Core shear failure of core 1
3	Divinycell H60	Aluminium	2x45° junction	6	1459 ± 18	Core shear failure of core 1
4	Divinycell H60		No junction	5	1167 ± 11	Core shear failure of core 1
5	Divinycell H200	Aluminium	Butt junction	7	1192 ± 37	Compr. face failure at junction
				8-2	991 ± 99	Delamination face / core 2
				9-2	954 ± 45	Delamination face / core 2

Figure 7. Observed fatigue failures for Config. 5 induced by local effects [9].

CONCLUSIONS

The paper has provided a brief overview of the mechanisms which determine the occurrence and severity of localized bending effects in sandwich structures with internal core junctions. The paper discusses two distinct cases; sandwich panels with internal core junctions subjected to in-

plane loading or transverse shear loading. For both cases it has been demonstrated that local effects are induced due to the material and geometric discontinuity at a core junction. The local effects lead to an increase of the face bending stresses as well as the core shear and transverse normal stresses. Moreover, the factors that influence the amplitude and extension of the local effects have been studied experimentally and through elaborate FE analyses for both load cases, and it has been shown that local effects induced by internal core junctions in sandwich panels may significantly influence the static and fatigue failure behaviour under certain conditions.

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